

ISic3477

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

list

Material

sandstone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Davide Massimo

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-07-23 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Recovered from the area of Temple A in 1956 (either from the main trench along the west side of the platform, or other soundings taken in the vicinity, all made by Carettoni in 1956)

Coordinates

38.000505, 14.261362

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 30587

Physical Description

Fragment of a limestone stele. The left margin is preserved, but the stone is broken on all other sides.

Dimensions

Height 13 cm

Width 8.5 cm

Depth 14 cm

Layout

The beginning of five lines of Greek letters more or less aligned with the left margin of the stone.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are regular and well spaced. Alpha has broken bar; epsilon has a shorter middle bar.

Letter heights:

Lines 1-5: 15-18 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. Ἐπ[ι][---]
2. Ἡρα[κλειδ][---]
3. Ἀπολ[λ][---]
4. Αἰσχύ[λος][---]
5. Εὐ[---]

Apparatus

Text as in Prag and Tigano 2017, from autopsy

Carettoni: ΑΠΟΛ[ΛΙΝΙ]

Carettoni: ΑΙΣΚΥ[---]

Translation

Commentary

Carettoni (1961: 318) suggested that this was a dedication to Apollo, restoring ΑΠΟΛΛΙΝΙ ('to Apollo') in line 3; Manganaro (1999: 68, followed by Facella 2006: 320) speculates instead that the text was a list of names, perhaps of ephebes, or alternatively of dedicants or contributors, but too little survives to be certain of either interpretation. It is possible that the text continued both above and/or below what survives. Carettoni mistakenly read ΑΙΣΚΥ in line 4. The restorations are those suggested by Manganaro, but must be considered purely *exempli gratia*.

The text cannot be dated precisely, but the letter forms suggest a date in the second or first century BC.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645098

PHI 336074

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1282

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 318 no.12a

Manganaro, G. 1999. *Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca*. Pisa, Roma. At 68 no.63 fig.145

Facella, A. 2006. *Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia tirrenica*. Pisa. At 320

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. *Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.1

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